

THE CONTENT AND POSSIBILITIES OF PREPARING FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS FOR INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: This article discusses the pedagogical possibilities of preparing future music teachers for innovative activities. Also, in the educational process, there will be discussions about the scientific theoretical basis of introducing the advanced pedagogical technologies that are effective today in the quality organization of music education into the educational process.

Key words: Music education, pedagogical technology, practice, methodology, individual and group work.

Introduction:

Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres, and to actively participate in such changes, high-level general and special knowledge, intellectual it is required to have potential, a broad outlook and skillful use of information communications. Based on these requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today.

At the first stage of the implementation of the goals and objectives of the "*National Program of Personnel Training*", it is defined "*Organization of the training of pedagogues and scientific pedagogues and their professional development at a level that meets the requirements of the time.*"

In the second stage, the technical and information base of educational institutions will be strengthened, the educational process will be provided with high-quality educational literature and advanced pedagogical technologies. In this sense, the implementation of advanced pedagogical technologies is also important. That is why it is one of the important requirements of today to further improve the teacher's professional skills, to organize the process of training pedagogical personnel based on a technological approach, and to prepare future teachers for this activity.

The technological approach to education is one of the factors that actively influence the pedagogical process and determine its effectiveness, integrity and success.

To pay attention to future teachers studying in higher educational institutions, including music teachers, who have thorough professional training based on the requirements of the present time and become skilled masters of their profession. Science and education moreover, it is one of the most pressing tasks of the personnel training system.

The more knowledgeable a teacher is, the more knowledgeable he is in his profession and the more skillful he is in using modern pedagogical technologies, the more he can raise the future generation to become a well-rounded and well-rounded person. In higher pedagogical education, future music teachers are trained for pedagogical activities and their

knowledge and skills from musical sciences - music teaching methodology, music theory and analysis, choir and choral studies, conducting, solfeggio, and most importantly, their attitude to their chosen professions, is important. In this regard, it should be noted that students studying in the field of musical education have different knowledge, level, musical training and attitude to the profession. Here they can be divided into three categories:

- ♪ Students who have a basic knowledge of music, who love their profession, who study diligently to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications in order to realize their dream of becoming a teacher in the future;
- ♪ Students who have a talent and ability for music, but are not interested in all subjects and do not feel that they are needed in their future career. They cannot thoroughly master various aspects of pedagogical activity.
- ♪ Students of this category were forced to enter the educational institution against their wishes, which affects their studies. They do not set the main goal of working in this field in the future while studying in the profession of pedagogy.

This activity will be effective and appropriate only if the preparation of future teachers for innovative activities during their studies is carried out as a whole with the work of preparing them for pedagogical activities. In the direction of musical education, the integration of subjects takes such a form that each subject in turn is the second, third, etc. It requires mastering the necessary skills and abilities, incorporating all musical, practical and theoretical knowledge. For example, music theory (means of musical expression), solfeggio, (note reading) analysis of musical works, and vocal singing, theoretical literacy, conducting, choral arrangement, analysis of works in choir and choral studies to acquire performance skills. a certain amount of knowledge is required. Therefore, each subject teacher should prepare students for pedagogical technology based on the specific characteristics of the subject he/she is teaching. Currently, the observation and analysis of work in this direction in the family education system shows that the majority of professors and teachers working in the field of musical education consider themselves to have nothing to do with preparing students for technological activities. . Doing this work is considered the work of teachers of "Pedagogy" or "Music Teaching Theory and Methodology", or they do not pay attention to this work at all. The reason for this is, firstly, that the professors are not ready for this activity, and secondly, they do not understand the nature of preparing the future pedagogues for technological activity as a social and political necessity.

The expected result can be achieved only if the preparation of future music teachers for technological activities is organized on the basis of an integrated system in the teaching of all subjects, not within one discipline. That is, subjects such as choral and choral studies, conducting, vocal performance, instrumental performance, music history, analysis of musical works, music teaching methodology (these subjects are considered to be important subjects in the student's future music teaching activities). in the process of training, if the preparation for the profession and the preparation for the technological process are carried out in an integral relationship with each other, and each of the events (sessions) is step by step, the educational process of future teachers is skillfully advanced pedagogical technology it becomes effective as a whole system only if it prepares to organize based on it.

Pedagogical practice plays an important role in preparing future teachers for the technological approach in the educational process. Currently, students at each stage of the musical education specialty go to study and qualification. Pedagogical practices of 2 weeks in

the first course, 4 weeks in the 2nd-3rd courses, and 14 weeks in the 4th course constitute an important period in their professional preparation. If the pedagogical and technological preparation of students is not taken into account in this process, then the same problem as we mentioned above will arise. Because it is more convenient, efficient and in line with modern requirements to acquire the skills of pedagogical technologies and their application in the course of the lesson compared to the practical work activity.

In the course of pedagogical practices, students identify their shortcomings, work on their correction, this process serves as a "general rehearsal before a big concert" for them, figuratively speaking. In this process, they will test themselves freely, the issue of their professional training, whether they can carry out pedagogical activities in connection with advanced pedagogical technologies or not will be clarified. At the same time, students can directly see and experience the various aspects of the teaching profession - difficult, difficult and creative - only during the pedagogical practice.

Our observations showed that the professional formation of future teachers is more active in the process of well-organized pedagogical practice. Because constant contact with advanced, experienced teachers helps to directly observe, learn, acquire and assimilate the best experiences of their creative work.

One of the most important skills that every teacher should acquire at the present time is the ability to organize and conduct lessons on the basis of pedagogical technologies. According to its composition, this skill is quite complex. for this:

In order to prepare students for innovative activities and to form related skills and qualifications, it is first necessary to be able to effectively use educational and cognitive activities, to achieve that students acquire the skills of using pedagogical technologies in the teaching of each subject. For example, during conducting training, "*Student Training*", "*I Conductor*", "*Cluster*", "*Brainstorming*", "*Scarabey*", "*Discussion*", "*Communication*", "*Group lib work*", "*Small group holiday work*", "*Individual work*", "*Dividing into differential groups*", "*Multimedia technology*", "*Concert lesson*", "*Difficult situation*" in the lessons of the basics of choir and choral studies. "*Quiz lesson*", "*Question - answer*", "*Continue the melody*", "*Lesson trip*", "*Competition lessons*" technologies can be used in the teaching of the instrument performance lesson and students can be prepared for such activities.

The technological preparation of students for pedagogical activity is important for the student to be able to consciously, reliably and successfully apply the theoretical psychological, pedagogical and methodical knowledge acquired during training sessions and which should be strengthened during practical training and pedagogical practices. depends on the aspect.

The main methods of preparing students for innovative technological activities in the educational process are as follows:

- *Tasks given to students to develop certain skills and systematic implementation of their theoretical and practical mastery;*
- *Independent practice of some methods of pedagogical technologies during the lesson in pedagogical practice;*
- *The teacher constantly monitors the student's mastery of pedagogical technologies and the ability to apply them in practice, giving advice;*
- *To discuss the acquired skills and qualifications of students in the use of pedagogical technologies in the class, in groups;*

- *Teach students to observe and analyze their own work and the work of their peers, and to evaluate it;*
- *Holding various contests and competitions among students, showing them examples of creative work, etc.*

The teacher chooses the technology used in the lesson according to the content and topic of the lesson, in which the main attention and goal is focused on achieving a specific result. Of course, the level of knowledge, interests and aspirations of students are taken into account here. For example, it is possible to listen to a musical work on a tape recorder, then discuss it, analyze it collectively around a round table, learn the necessary information about the work (theoretical, artistic - text) on the basis of a free discussion. It is also possible to creatively use visual aids, handouts, various literature, and information sources.

Along with the teacher, it is necessary to plan the teaching process in advance. In this process, the teacher should take into account the content of the educational material, the possibility of the class, and turn the students into the center of the lesson activity.

It is very important for the teacher to make a technological map of the upcoming lesson in order to plan the lesson to a level that can lead to a good result, because the technological map of the lesson is created based on the capabilities and needs of the students from each subject, each training feature. Creating such a technological map has its own complexities. For this, the teacher should be aware of pedagogy, psychology, special methodology, informatics and information technologies, as well as know a lot of methods and methods. Making each lesson colorful, interesting and meaningful depends in many respects on the planned technological map of the lesson, which has been carefully thought out in advance.

How to create a technological map of the lesson depends on the experience and the set goal. No matter how the technological map is structured, it is important that the lesson process is reflected as a whole and that a clearly defined goal, task and guaranteed result are expressed. Creating a technological map allows the teacher to write an extended overview of the lesson. Because all aspects of the lesson are reflected in such a map.

The technological map prepared by the teacher for each subject of the subject taught by the teacher allows him to understand how to approach each lesson as a whole, from the beginning of the entire educational process, from the purpose, to the results to be achieved. provides an opportunity to organize a lesson.

The advanced pedagogical technologies used in the course of the lesson help students to think freely, creatively approach every issue, to feel responsibility, to work independently, to analyze, to make good use of scientific and methodical literature, textbooks, and most importantly, science, should increase their interest in acquiring knowledge and skills on the subject.

Monitoring the students during the lesson is a separate process and is carried out according to the purpose and content of each lesson. The most real and correct and effective form of control is self-control. This is equally necessary for the teacher and the student.

Just as the teaching of each subject has its own characteristics, the music teacher has his own "secrets", that is, his method, his own approach, organization, organization, and the ability to communicate with children. will be Among these, the common features are love for the art of music, one's profession, careful preparation for lessons, giving students more knowledge and understanding, striving to fully and perfectly master the taught topics. , selflessly, to live the life of a teacher.

A music teacher carries out educational and educational work at the same time. He should not only have extensive knowledge in his specialty, but should also have good knowledge of other subjects related to music, literature, visual arts. A person who educates students musically, artistically, and aesthetically should have the worldview, understanding of thinking, loyalty to his profession, and continuous improvement of his skills. As we have already mentioned, a music teacher should have a good knowledge of playing instruments, playing musical instruments, vocal singing, and theoretical knowledge during the period of higher education. Because the tune and song performed live has the most rapid and emotional impact. Live music and songs quickly attract the attention of students and create a good mood. Allows you to return the desired tact (sentence) during group singing. And finally, the teacher who skillfully plays the musical instrument and sings the song in a beautiful voice shows his students how interesting and attractive it is to play music by everyone. A music teacher is not limited to skillfully playing musical instruments, but also has a good sound, conducting skills, and skills of working with a team, which guarantees the effectiveness of his work.

In addition to these, it is good for the teacher to monitor the lessons, record his achievements and shortcomings in a special notebook, and prepare accordingly for the next lessons. Due to constant observations, the pedagogical skill of the teacher grows and develops. He learns to assess the situation, to feel the mood of students, how the lesson left an impression on them, their inner feelings. It is desirable that observation be carried out under the principle of "continuity" from the first grade to the seventh grade. In addition, in addition to the use of pedagogical technology, in addition to self-performance, in each lesson, the content, authors, period of creation, genre, character, form, tempo, tone - tonality should provide the necessary understanding of performance characteristics.

In the lesson of music culture, the teacher's vocabulary should be at a high level. The introduction of the teacher about the studied piece and the explanation of the subject of the lesson will bring the students into the wonderful and magical world of music. The fact that the main basis of such qualities, skills, qualifications are created in the educational process during the period of higher education and continuously improved, enriched and developed in the teaching activity defines the main content of the social order placed before the pedagogue-coaches and their professional activity.

Conclusions:

The perspective of any society depends on its status of education and training, the structure and essence of the new education system, and deep educational culture. After all, the level of education is the only factor that ensures the future of the society, the state and the nation, and determines its influence in the world. With its status and content, it is a value that has no alternative.

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